

A VIRTUAL TESTING APPROACH TO MATERIALS SELECTION FOR IMPACT SHIELDING APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

A workflow supported by high-fidelity virtual testing for the selection of candidate materials to be incorporated into shielding protection systems is presented. Modeling techniques for the accurate simulation of impact events on carbon-based composite shields hybridized with several materials of standout ballistic performance are described. A Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) approach is adopted for the computational implementation of coupled failure mechanisms (fiber breakage, interlaminar delamination, matrix cracking, through-the-thickness shear plugging, friction) that take place in composites during projectile penetration. Complementary energy dissipation modes attained through the multi-layer hybridization with other ballistic materials are accounted for in the simulations and combined with the baseline carbon laminates to achieve optimum layouts. The work focuses on UD laminates discretized with a strategy of regularized oriented meshes with an extended 3D version of the Maimí damage model. User material VUMAT Fortran subroutines developed by IMDEA Materials are employed in the simulations. The resulting virtual testing models allow to capture properly complex patterns of failure mechanisms in multi-material shield arrangements, thus supporting this computational framework as a valuable alternative to the expensive and time-consuming physical testing to assess the energy absorption capability of hybrid shields.

1 INTRODUCTION

The lightness requirement for airframes shielding against external menaces such as bird strike, blade release, impact of ice, runway debris or fragments expelled during engine failure events [1] is urging upon researchers the need of combining properly multiple energy absorption/dissipation mechanisms in modern impact protection systems. In high-performance structural composites with traditional laminate architecture, these mechanisms are activated through coupled failure modes as fiber breakage, interlaminar delamination, matrix cracking, through-the-thickness shear plugging and friction during the penetration [2, 3]. A survey of other materials with potential airworthiness qualification and energy absorption capability reveals that complementary dissipation can be achieved by mechanisms like core crushing in sandwich structures, plastic deformation in metals, brittle fracture and spallation of ceramic tiles, or membrane-like deformation up to yarns breakage of dry fabrics manufactured from synthesized ballistic fibers such as aramids, UHMWPE or PBO [4].

For aeronautical applications, current investigations are specially focused on the development of hybrid multi-material shields designed with progressive stiffness gradient in the through-the-thickness direction [5]. These configurations typically promote the softening and redistribution of the impact loads over the regions surrounding the impact point, thus maximizing the arresting capability of dry fabrics stacked at the back face of the shield by mitigation of the out-of-plane load peaks that tend to

puncture the fabrics. Materials able to erode and/or fragment the projectiles are typically positioned at the impact face, this is the case of ceramics, which also offer the capability of spreading the affected impact area by cone and radial cracking patterns, improving the performance of the background layers of the shield. The resulting hybrid shielding configurations are subjected to multiple interacting failure mechanisms associated to different material constitutive responses and to the arrangement of the different materials inside the shield, which strongly determines the role and behaviour of each constituent. Consequently, the construction of optimized shielding designs with progressive stiffness gradient according to the aforementioned guidelines requires the aid of computational resources in order to avoid expensive and time-consuming experimental campaigns. Here, virtual testing [6, 7] arises as a framework of advanced computational techniques able to retrieve high-fidelity simulations at multiple length scales [8] and of multiple damage processes, e.g. virtual test of composite coupons [9], low-velocity impacts (LVI) and subsequent damage tolerance analysis on small panels [10, 11], and, of course, high-velocity impacts (HVI) [5], in which the dynamic response of the impacted composite material is highly non-linear, leading to large deformations and distortions of the finite elements (FE) used in the computational discretization. Moreover, the virtual design of shields for ballistic applications must deal with specific challenges associated to the simulation in the high-velocity range, such as the consideration of inertial and strain rate effects.

This work presents a comprehensive overview of virtual testing modeling techniques and capabilities for the appropriate simulation and further selection of shielding configurations. The overview refers to experimental and numerical investigations carried out for the characterization of materials for ballistic applications, enumerates the contributions of different authors to the development of advanced damage models for fiber reinforced plastic composites (FRP), describes FE modeling techniques in the meso-scale and presents several validations of computational results obtained with Abaqus/Explicit, complemented with additional simulations and failure mechanisms analysis of carbon-based hybrid shields under study for their use in ballistic protection applications.

2 COMPUTATIONAL MODELING OF IMPACT ON HYBRID SHIELDS

2.1 Material models

Since the reliability of the material properties and the damage models to be employed in virtual tests are of major importance for the correct representation of the failure mechanisms and the accurate quantification of energy dissipation during an impact event, this section gathers a (non-exhaustive) collection of references where researchers can find valuable characterizations of materials suited for crashing applications.

Metals: a complete study on the energy absorption capability of aluminum plates can be found in Iqbal and Gupta (2008) and Buyuk *et al.* (2008), who presented an experimental-numerical investigation of the behaviour of 2024-T3/T351 alloy under impact loading for airplane engine containment and fragment shielding. In 1999, Lesuer had published an experimental work on material models for Ti-6Al-4V and 2024-T3. In a FAA report in 2003, Kay presented an implementation of damage on Ti-6Al-4V and 2024-T3 using the Johnson-Cook material model [12, 13]. The Johnson-Cook model is a recognized benchmark for the numerical simulation of damage in high strain metals, such as aluminum, which takes into account strain rate and thermal effects [5]. It is available as a built-in code in Abaqus/Explicit libraries, what facilitates its use in combination with other materials which require external user subroutines. An example of this synergy is the validation included in Garijo *et al.* (2017) [5] of Fiber Metal Laminates (FML, indeed hybrid configurations) models developed for HVI (Figure 3c). Recent NASA reports show a long lasting interest of the scientific community in the use of Ti-6Al-4V and 2024 alloys for shielding applications (Pereira *et al.*, 2013). Other researchers have focused their investigations on steel armors, better suited for automotive and civil industries than for the aerospace sector, see for instance Børvik *et al.* (2002 & 2009), Dey *et al.* (2007) or Deb *et al.* (2008).

Fiber reinforced composites: modern literature provides numerous approaches for the FE simulation of impact damage in FRP composites [2, 3]. From a Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) standpoint, the characterization of the structural deterioration of orthotropic media via generalized material constitutive laws is based on damage onset and propagation criteria developed by

many contributors: pioneering failure criteria for UD laminates by Hashin (1980); crack band theory by Bažant and Oh (1983); failure criteria for FRP laminates by Dávila *et al.* (2005) and Pinho *et al.* (2005 & 2006); in-situ strengths and matrix cracking assessment by Camanho *et al.* (2006); plane-stress LaRC CDM model for FRP by Maimí *et al.* (2007) [14, 15]; mesh regularization strategy for correct energy dissipation during delamination with cohesive FE by Turon *et al.* (2007); 3D extension of LaRC model by Lopes *et al.* (2009) [10]; revisited 3D failure criteria for UD FRP by Catalanotti *et al.* (2013); and, more recently, the introduction of layer-by-layer aligned mesh lines with orthotropic material directions proposed by Lopes *et al.* [11] (2016) in order to mitigate the mesh-induced crack propagation direction bias. The strategy of oriented regularized meshes accounting for material-discretization interdependences (Figure 1) is the one adopted in this work for the numerical simulation of ballistic impacts on UD laminates. Thus, the CDM code for FRP is plugged into Abaqus/Explicit through a VUMAT user Fortran subroutine. Since failure mechanisms in multi-layer composite arrangements develop at two meso-mechanical levels (intra- and interlaminar damage), a damage model is also required to properly represent delamination at interfaces between layers. Further modeling details in this regard are provided in Section 2.2, which describes meso-mechanical architectures for targets under HVI.

Figure 1: Features for the computational implementation of 3D-extended CDM model for FRP laminates, IMDEA Materials Institute: (a) meso-mechanical unit built with (b) solid FE and cohesive interlaminar relationships; (c) fracture modes in FRP and associated CDM internal variables; (d) mesh regularization for models with material-oriented meshes.

Core structures: hybridization of monolithic laminates can take advantage of the outstanding properties of sandwich structures in terms of stiffness-to-weight ratio. Furthermore, once the mechanical response of materials acting as skins (e.g. carbon laminates) is accurately modeled (e.g. following the aforementioned guidelines), the incorporation of cores with projectile arresting capability represents a design variant of unquestionable interest for airframe engineers. Beyond conventional cores such as PVC foams (Ivañez *et al.*, 2011) or honeycombs manufactured from Nomex™, Kevlar™, fiberglass, carbon or thermoplastics, fancy architectures are being attained thanks to the flexibility of novel manufacturing techniques. Foldcores (e.g. made of Kevlar™ or CFRP laminate, see Heimbs [16], 2008) constitute a new generation of cellular structures developed to overcome the drawbacks of water ingress of honeycombs in aircraft structures. Once unit cell FE models with the detail of the core architecture are subjected to virtual compression tests, a constitutive stress-strain curve [16] can be retrieved and further used in a homogenized core material with a tabular plastic response and an approach of ductile damage under compression for the erosion of the elements. The core constituent can be simply represented with a structured mesh of solid elements between external skins. This modeling strategy is computationally efficient and eases noticeably the simulation of sandwich structures. Similar procedures can be followed to incorporate other non-conventional cores such as corrugated hybrid fiberglass-foam cores (Russell *et al.*, 2010), hollow pyramidal lattice truss cores (Queheillalt and Wadley, 2011), hybrid foam-braided carbon fiber composite lattice truss cores (George *et al.*, 2014) or negative stiffness cores (Correa *et al.*, 2015).

Ceramic armors: ceramic materials incorporated into hybrid multi-layered composite backing layouts are commonly used for impact protection against small fragments and armor piercing projectiles (Krishnan *et al.*, 2010; Tasdemirci *et al.*, 2012; Signetti and Pugno, 2014; Tan, 2014). Alumina (Al_2O_3), Boron Carbide (B_4C) and Silicon Carbide (SiC) are some of the most widely employed ceramics for this purpose. For aerospace applications, these materials are specifically aimed at engine failure containment systems, due to the difficulties for their implementation in large wet surfaces of the aircraft, e.g. fuselage shielding. Ceramic materials present a brittle fracture due to their low maximum strain deformation. Under impact load, a compressive shock wave is generated and propagates through the thickness of ceramic plates. After further reflection of the shock wave, tensile fracture takes place by a failure mechanism known as spallation. Besides, radial cracks typically initiate at the bottom of the ceramic material due to spalling (Figure 3d). A fracture cone is generated at the impact zone on the top of the ceramic tile and grows towards the back face nucleating coaxial cylindrical cracks. Due to the high strength of ceramic materials, additional energy dissipation can be achieved by significant erosion that metallic projectiles may suffer. Generally, all these failure mechanisms promote the softening of the impact load over a wider area. Thus, maximum efficiency is accomplished by positioning the ceramic layers at the impact face of the shields. From computational standpoint, a FE discretization based on 3D elements combined with a damage model for brittle materials such as the one developed in 1994 by Johnson and Holmquist (see Bürger *et al.* [17], 2009), today available in Abaqus/Explicit libraries allow the reproduction of the complex patterns of fracture in ceramics (Figure 3d). Detailed virtual testing of hybrid ceramic/composite shields is presented in Section 3.2.

Ballistic dry fabrics: dry fabrics manufactured from synthesized fibers (e.g. aramids, UHMWPE or PBO) represent a family of recognized energy absorption capability and competitive performance referred to their weight. These fabrics provide the possibility of being installed as constituents of multi-layer configurations, in their dry form or embedded in a matrix, offering a rich variety of designs adaptable to specific applications. Since the first commercialization of Kevlar™ in the mid-1970s, the aeronautical industry has considered these fabrics for jet engine blade containment systems, and the technological interest for this application is increasing today with the development of new fibers of diverse chemical structure (Pereira and Revilock [4], 2009). A comprehensive compilation of candidate fibers for ballistic protection can be found in Utracki [18] (2010): Kevlar™, Twaron™, Technora™, Heracron™, Nomex™, Innegra™, M5™, Vectran™, Spectra™, Dyneema™ or Zylon™ are examples of materials under study. The present work fosters the investigation via virtual testing of progressive stiffness gradient designs [5] with ballistic dry fabrics positioned at the back faces of the shields. The FE simulations presented in Section 3.2 adopt a 2D approach of CDM model implemented by IMDEA Materials Institute, with planar or solid elements programmed with plane

stress (membrane) stress tensor.

2.2 Meso-mechanical FE architectures

Literature provides numerous approaches to the modeling of composites and multi-layered laminates subjected to dynamic loads at a meso-scale level (e.g. Yaghoobi and Liaw, 2012; Pernas-Sánchez *et al.*, 2014; Schwab *et al.*, 2016; Zarei *et al.*, 2017). This section focuses on the models developed by IMDEA Materials Institute for the simulation of coupons manufactured from UD carbon/epoxy material (Lopes *et al.* [11], 2016; Falcó *et al.* [9], 2017), validated for application to HVI in Garijo *et al.* [5] (2017). In the present work, these models are extended to hybrid shielding configurations with composite structural baseline, in particular laminates with backing ballistic dry fabrics, sandwich structures and hybrids with ceramic armor (Section 3.2).

The carbon/epoxy laminate FE discretization is illustrated in Figure 2, combined with a damageable homogenized core material constituted by solid elements, as described in Section 2.1. At the inner regions of interest of the sandwich skins, a layer-by-layer mesh regularization strategy with mesh lines aligned with the intrinsic fiber direction is adopted. The regularized oriented meshes facilitate the predominant matrix fracture cracks extension in parallel direction to UD fiber. Due to the resulting non-conformity of the meshes at the interfaces between layers, the interlaminar interactions are managed through a Cohesive Zone Model (CZM) approach with the technology of cohesive surfaces available in Abaqus. An interlaminar mixed-mode cohesive-frictional behavior is incorporated, using a quadratic stress initiation criterion and an energy-type damage evolution law with a mixed-mode Benzeggagh–Kenane [5]. The CZM approach is also selected to govern the interactions between skins and core in Figure 2. The two-level damage architecture is completed by a 3D version of the LaRC CDM model for the intralaminar degradation, coded in a VUMAT subroutine. The element deletion criteria are enhanced with additional strain-based conditions as exposed in [5].

Figure 2: FE modeling strategy for sandwich targets subjected to ballistic impact.

Figure 3: Damage patterns retrieved by virtual testing of different candidate materials for impact shielding applications, simulations performed by IMDEA Materials Institute.

3 VIRTUAL IMPACT TESTS OF HYBRID SHIELDS

3.1 Validation of virtual models for carbon/epoxy and FML composites

The formal validation of the CDM-CZM approach with regularized oriented meshes for multi-layered targets composed by UD fiber/epoxy and metallic materials in the HVI regime is published in Garijo *et al.* [5] (2017). Here, the validation is updated and completed with additional results for carbon-based laminates. Figure 4 gathers the comparison of numerical and experimental ballistic curves for square panels of AS4/8552 with stacking sequences $[(45/90/-45/0)_2]_S$ and $[(45/90/-45/0)_4]_S$ impacted by spherical steel balls of diameters $D = 20$ mm and $D = 30$ mm in the velocity range $V_i = 40 - 140$ m/s. The diagrams show excellent agreement between numerical and experimental data in all the impact scenarios tested. This rise in the robustness of the FE technique is achieved by means of an evolved VUMAT subroutine in which features like refined strain-based element deletion criteria, volumetric strain-gradient control or revision of the damage onset and evolution due to out-of-plane crushing stress have been included. The study of FML (GLARETM) composites presented in [5], based on beam specimens clamped at their edges as referred by Yaghoubi and Liaw (2012), has also been extended, in this case with numerical simulations of spherical (Figure 3c) and cylindrical (Figure 5c) projectiles shot against square panels, taking as reference the experimental data published by Zarei *et al.* (2017).

Besides the accuracy of the results presented in Figure 4, the pursued high-fidelity of the simulations is retrieved, as it can be observed in the snapshots of the failure mechanisms illustrated in Figure 5. The breakage patterns captured in carbon composites include matrix cracks propagating in parallel to the local fiber directions, coupled plugging-membrane failure at the impact point,

Figure 4: Experimental and numerical ballistic curves of impacts on AS4/8552 laminates.

cohesive damage area of similar size and shape than the delaminated area observed in C-scan inspections, etc. The simulation of impact on FML targets reproduces the plugging and radial cracking of the rear aluminum layers, combined with the formation of plastic lips, intralaminar damage dominated by matrix failure at the fiberglass plies and effective interlaminar failure at the aluminum-fiberglass and fiberglass-fiberglass interfaces.

3.2 Investigation of failure mechanisms in candidate shielding configurations

The validation described in Section 3.1 constitutes a starting point for the development of models of hybrid shields based on carbon/epoxy laminates. In these arrangements, the extrapolation of the CDM-CZM approach with regularized meshes must account for the additional interactions of the carbon/epoxy laminates with adjacent constituents, e.g. adhesion with core in sandwich structure or contact interaction with other fragmented layers. This section includes results of impact simulations on three representative hybrid shields: panels with woven dry fabrics of ballistic fibers attached at the back face, sandwich panels with carbon/epoxy skins and composite panels provided with a ceramic armor.

The addition of dry fabrics at the back face of a shield can be performed according to the scheme of Figure 6a, in which the role and behavior of the different constituents of a panel with progressive stiffness gradient in the through-the-thickness direction are compiled. Materials like KevlarTM, DyneemaTM or ZylonTM may have operative limitations due to their degradation under some environmental conditions, but in nominal conditions provide outstanding performances, with maximum ballistic strength-to-weight ratios. Dry fabrics are not structural elements, then they have to be implemented as add-ons of components fulfilling strength and stiffness requirements. The typical

(a) UD laminate of 32 plies of AS4/8552 impacted by spherical projectile ($D=30\text{mm}$) at 100 m/s

(b) Comparison of experimental and numerical delamination areas in impact of spherical projectile ($D=30\text{mm}$) at 120 m/s against a 32 plies UD laminate of AS4/8552 (C-scan, right)

(c) GLARETM 2/1 target impacted by cylindrical projectile at 100 m/s

Figure 5: Failure mechanisms captured via virtual testing of carbon laminates (a, b) and FML (c) with FE strategy using regularized oriented meshes incorporated into a CDM-CZM approach.

arresting mechanism of dry fabrics, with stressed yarns in cross-like patterns, is reproduced in the sequence shown in Figure 6b.

The perforation of a sandwich panel by a spherical projectile is illustrated in Figure 7. The sandwich skins are manufactured from AS4/8552, while the core is simulated with brick elements that contain a homogenized compressive stress-strain response (including elastic-plastic behavior and subsequent softening) corresponding to an aramid foldcore as per Heimbs [16]. The core contributes to the dissipation of the kinetic energy of the projectile by means of a ductile damage model, resulting in deleted elements along a conical track of decreasing area in the through-the-thickness direction, from impact face to back face. The interactions between core and skins are introduced by means of a CZM model similar to the one used to describe the interlaminar cohesion between the carbon/epoxy plies. The effect of the presence of cores on the damage patterns obtained in the skins and on the final residual velocity of the projectile is matter of interest (Ivañez *et al.*, 2011). Note the different damages produced at the impact and back skins in Figure 7, and the similarities with the damage patterns reported in [5].

Finally, the result of a simulation of the high velocity impact of a steel ball against a carbon/epoxy laminate with a ceramic armor composed by SiC tiles is shown in Figure 8. As a consequence of the impact, kinetic energy is dissipated in all the participants in the collision: composite breakage (CDM-CZM model), brittle fracture in the ceramic tiles (Johnson-Holmquist model) and projectile erosion

Figure 6: Design and virtual testing of shields provided with woven dry fabrics of ballistic fibers at the back face to act as arresting bags (driven by membrane deformation).

Figure 7: Failure mechanisms retrieved by virtual testing of sandwich structure with carbon skins.

Figure 8: Description of the FE discretization of a hybrid shield composed by ceramic tiles and structural carbon/epoxy laminate, and resulting failure mechanisms retrieved in HVI.

(Johnson-Cook model), as gathered in [Figure 8e](#). The initial crash of the steel ball with a pyramidal ceramic tile and further contact with the backing composite generates, at early stages of the penetration, large matrix cracks in the laminate propagating along the preferential direction, corresponding to the orientation of the last layer (45°). This phenomenon, observed in experimental tests of UD composites [\[5, 10, 11\]](#), is dictated by the governing flexural stiffness of the laminate.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The design and optimization of hybrid shields for ballistic protection is a challenging task that requires a solid knowledge of the intrinsic physical phenomena that occur during HVI events. These include complex and heterogeneous failure mechanisms in each of the constituents, determined not only by the constitutive laws that govern their mechanical response, but also affected by the specific conditions of the impact (inertial and strain rate effects, edge constraints, type of projectile...) and by

the particular interactions derived from the arrangement of materials within the shield. The experimental approach for the characterization of the impact behavior of candidate shielding materials is a valuable source of information that engineers have available in the literature. But without the assistance of numerical tools able to encompass all the aforementioned considerations, the cost and time spent in experimental campaigns maybe prohibitive due to the large amount of potential hybrid shielding configurations to be tested. This work focuses on a virtual testing approach for the design and selection of hybrid shielding configurations. Emphasis is placed on the survey of reliable references for the proper definition of parameters of different material models (metals, fiber reinforced composites, sandwich cores, ceramics and ballistic fabrics). A validated FE strategy with regularized meshes is taken as basis for the simulation of carbon/epoxy laminates. The simulations presented make use of this technique and show a procedure to integrate it into highly detailed models of hybrid shields, in combination with other architectures and materials. The fidelity of failure mechanisms reached indicates the high potential of the virtual testing as an advanced computational framework to drive the design of structures subjected to dynamic loads.

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